

INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE PROPERTIES OF STITCHED FIBREGLASS COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: This paper assesses the ability of two theoretical models to predict the Mode I and Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness properties of fibre reinforced polymer composites reinforced by through-the-thickness stitching. The models were used to calculate R-curves and steady state energy release rates for stitched glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) composites. The GFRP was stitched in two orientations with Kevlar[®] thread to two densities. The Mode I model predicted a significant increase in the delamination resistance of the stitched composites, and the magnitude of this improvement was confirmed experimentally using the double cantilever beam (DCB) test. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) showed that this toughening was caused by stitches bridging the delamination and, to a lesser extent, by crack tip deflection and by stitch pull-out processes. The Mode II model predicted that stitching would only provide a small improvement in delamination toughness, and this was in reasonable agreement with experimental results determined with the end notch cantilever (ENC) test which showed no appreciable change in toughness as a result of stitching. SEM was used to observe the failure mechanisms of the stitches under Mode II loading, and it appears that the ability of stitching to improve the delamination resistance was masked by the unusually high toughness of the unstitched GFRP laminate. This study shows that the theoretical models can predict with reasonable accuracy the delamination resistance of stitched GFRP loaded in translaminar tension or shear.

KEYWORDS: glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) composite, stitching, mode I and mode II interlaminar fracture toughness, modelling

INTRODUCTION

Fibreglass composites are used in a wide variety of sporting goods, civil structures, automotive and aerospace components, and marine vessels. For example, these composites are used in sporting equipment such as fishing rods, javelins, pole vault poles and tennis rackets while in automobiles they have been used in structural chassis components such as drive shafts, springs and road wheels. Fibreglass is used in marine structures ranging in size from masts and radomes to racing yachts, fishing trawlers and minehunting ships. Despite the widespread use of glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) composites, their use in other applications has been restricted by low mechanical, fracture toughness and impact resistant properties in the through-thickness direction. This is a result of the two-dimensional (2-D) laminate structure, in which glass fibres do not extend in the through-thickness direction.

Since the mid-1980s there has been great interest in reinforcing composites by through-the-thickness stitching. Interlaminar fracture toughness studies reviewed by Dransfield *et al.* [1] show that stitched composites possess higher delamination resistance under Mode I and Mode II loading than traditional 2D laminates. For example, Jain [2] reports that the Mode I steady state energy release rate (G_{IRs}) required for crack propagation for a stitched carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite was 16 times higher than the unstitched CFRP laminate, while under Mode II loading the steady state values (G_{IIRs}) for CFRP composites was increased up to fourfold by stitching.

As a result of these improvements in interlaminar fracture toughness, stitched composites are being used in new structural applications such as the wings and fuselage of some aircraft [3]. An important requirement for assessing potential applications for stitched composites is a capability to accurately predict the improvement in delamination resistance resulting from stitching without the need for costly and time-consuming fracture toughness testing. Jain and Mai [4,5] have recently developed theoretical models for predicting the delamination crack growth resistance (R) curves of stitched composites under Mode I and Mode II loading. Jain [2] found that these models predicted the R-curves for a stitched CFRP composite with reasonably good accuracy when compared with experimentally measured R-curves. Despite this agreement, the models have not been rigorously tested for other types of stitched composite, and therefore the aim of this paper is to assess their accuracy against experimentally measured Mode I and Mode II R-curves for a GFRP composite stitched with Kevlar thread.

INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS MODELLING OF STITCHED COMPOSITES

Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Model

The model developed by Jain and Mai [4] for calculating the Mode I interlaminar toughness is based on Euler-Bernoulli linear elastic beam theory applied to a stitched composite with a double cantilever beam (DCB) geometry, as shown in Fig 1a. The model can be used to determine the effect of various stitching parameters (*eg.* stitch density, stitch modulus, thread diameter) on the R-curve behaviour of composites. However, the influence of stitching orientation cannot be determined. Jain and Mai [4] show that the Mode I delamination resistance in terms of stress intensity factor, $K_{IR}(\Delta a)$, of a composite with continuous through-the-thickness stitching can be calculated from the expression:

$$K_{IR}(\Delta a) = Y \frac{P}{\sqrt{H}} f\left(\frac{a_o + \Delta a}{H}\right) \quad (1)$$

where: a_o is the initial crack length
 Δa is crack growth characterised by the stitch bridging zone length
 $f(\cdot)$ is a geometric factor
 H is the half-thickness of the DCB specimen
 P is the crack propagation load at a known length $a_o + \Delta a$, and
 Y is an orthotropic correction factor.

These and the following parameters are defined in detail in Ref. [4]. The crack propagation load, P , is obtained from the following crack propagation condition:

$$K_{IR}(\Delta a) = Y \frac{P}{\sqrt{H}} f\left(\frac{a_o + \Delta a}{H}\right) = K_{IC} + Y \int_{t=0}^{\Delta a} p(t) \frac{1}{\sqrt{H}} f\left(\frac{t}{H}\right) dt \quad (2)$$

where: K_{IC} is the critical stress intensity factor of the (unstitched) composite
 $p(t)$ is the closure traction due to bridging stitches, and
 t is the distance from the crack tip to the specimen end.

Once the crack propagation load is known, the fracture toughness, $K_{IR}(\Delta a)$, can be calculated using equation 1, and the fracture toughness in terms of energy release rate, $G_{IR}(\Delta a)$, may be obtained using:

$$G_{IR}(\Delta a) = \frac{K_{IR}^2(\Delta a)}{E_o} \quad (3)$$

where E_o is the orthotropic elastic modulus of the composite [4].

Mode II Interlaminar Fracture Model

The Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness model by Jain and Mai [5] was derived using first order shear deformation laminated plate theory and Griffith's energy release rate approach. Models have been developed for stitched composites subjected to shear loading using the end notched flexure (ENF) or end notched cantilever (ENC) test methods. Fig 1b shows a diagram for the ENC specimen geometry, and the energy release rate available for crack propagation for this specimen is given by the following expression [5]:

$$G_{II} = \frac{A^*}{\cosh^2(\lambda \Delta a)} \left\{ \tau \left(\frac{\sinh(\lambda \Delta a)}{\lambda} + a_o + \alpha H \right) - \frac{\lambda}{A^*} \left(\frac{\alpha_1}{\alpha_2} \right) \sinh(\lambda \Delta a) \right\}^2 \quad (4)$$

where: τ is the shear stress and is related to the applied load P
 A^* is the correction factor to include shear deformation
 α_1 & α_2 are stitching parameters and
 α is related to material properties through A^* and α_1 .

The expressions for τ , A^* , α , α_1 , α_2 , and λ may be found in Ref. [5]. Using the crack propagation condition, $G_{II} = G_{IIc}$, where G_{IIc} is the critical energy release rate for the unstitched composite, the shear stress τ required for crack propagation can be determined. The energy release rate can then be calculated from:

$$G_{IIR} = A^* \tau^2 (a + \alpha H)^2 \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1: The (a) DCB and (b) ENC specimen geometry with through-the-thickness stitching used as a basis for the modelling of Modes I and II interlaminar fracture toughness

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Stitched GFRP Composites

Fibreglass composites were made with E-glass and a cold-curing vinyl ester resin. Two types of fibreglass, made by ACI Fibreglass Pty. Ltd., were used in each composite: a plain woven roving fabric (with an areal density of 0.6 kg/m^2) and a chopped strand mat (0.3 kg/m^2). These fibreglass materials were layered in an alternating sequence to 14 plies. This choice of material and layup was selected because it is used in many GFRP composite structures. Some of the fibreglass preforms were stitched using a modified lock stitch with 40 tex (2 x 20 tex) spun Kevlar[®]-49 yarn, which had a diameter of 0.16 mm. The stitching was performed in straight parallel rows along the length or across the width of the fracture toughness specimens (Fig. 2) to a density of 3 or 6 stitches/cm².

The preforms were resin transfer moulded with Derakane[®] 411-45 vinyl ester resin, which is produced by the Dow Chemical Company. The resin content of the composites was about 40% by weight, and the resin was cold-cured under ambient conditions ($\sim 20^\circ\text{C}$) for several weeks before fracture toughness testing.

Fig. 2: Geometry of the DCB specimens stitched in the (a) parallel and (b) normal directions

Interlaminar Fracture Toughness Testing

The Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness was measured using the DCB method in accordance with ASTM D5528-94a. The specimen geometry is shown in Fig 2. A 50 mm long Teflon film was located between the mid-thickness plies at one end of the specimen to initiate the delamination. End blocks were attached to this end of the specimen. Load was applied at a cross-head speed of 2 mm/min until the crack grew by 4-6 mm, and at this point the load (P) and cross-head displacement (δ) were recorded and the crack length (a) was measured using a travelling optical microscope before the specimen was unloaded and then reloaded until the crack grew by a further 4-6 mm. This process was repeated 12 times in a DCB test, which caused the delamination to grow by an average of 80 mm. Five DCB tests were performed on each composite. The Mode I energy release rate required for crack propagation was calculated using the elastic beam equation derived by Hashemi, Kinloch and Williams [6]:

$$G_{IR} = \frac{3P\delta}{2b(a + \chi H)} \quad (6)$$

where b is the specimen width and χ is a constant to correct for deflection and rotation effects at the crack tip, and is calculated using equations in Ref [6].

The Mode II fracture toughness was measured using the ENC method. The ENC specimen geometry was similar to the DCB specimens (Fig 2) except the pre-crack and specimen lengths were about 70 and 135 mm, respectively. The ENC specimens were loaded at a cross-head speed of 2 mm/min until the delamination grew a short distance (usually within 10 mm of the pre-crack). The load, cross-head displacement and crack length were then measured before the specimen was unloaded and reloaded. This process was repeated 8 times during a ENC test, which caused the delamination to grow by an average of 60 mm. Each composite was tested 5 times, and the Mode II energy release rate causing crack propagation was calculated from the expression [6]:

$$G_{IIR} = \frac{9P^2a^2}{4b^2H^3E_{11}} \quad (7)$$

where E_{11} is the Young's modulus of the composite.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Properties

Fig. 3 compares R-curves measured for the stitched composites under Mode I loading against theoretical R-curves calculated using equation 3. Also shown is a typical R-curve measured for the unstitched GFRP. The theoretical model is seen to calculate the Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of the stitched composites with reasonably good accuracy. The theoretical R-curves predict a rapid increase in fracture toughness within the first 8 mm of crack growth. This is due to the formation of a stitch bridging zone behind the delamination crack front (as

represented in Fig. 1 as the region Δa). Once this zone has fully developed, the model predicts steady-state delamination growth where the G_{IR} value remains constant with further crack growth. The measured R-curves show however that the G_{IR} value does not remain constant,

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3: Theoretical and measured Mode I R-curves for the GFRP composites stitched to a (a) low and (b) high stitch density. The theoretical R-curves are shown by the solid line

and this is because the delamination grew in a slip/stick process. In the DCB tests it was observed that when the delamination approached a row of stitches the crack growth speed was slowed until some of the stitches bridging the delamination failed under a higher load. This then allowed the delamination to propagate rapidly to the next row of stitches where the process repeated itself. This slip/stick fracture process contributed to the scatter in the G_{IR} values of the stitched composites, which is represented by the error bars in Fig. 3.

A comparison of the measured and calculated G_{IRs} values is presented in Table 1. The calculated toughness values are the same for stitching in the parallel and normal directions because the model does not account for stitch orientation. The measured values, however, show that stitch direction has a negligible influence on toughness. Good agreement is seen between the measured and predicted G_{IRs} values, although the model predicts a slightly higher value for the high stitch density composites.

Table 1: Comparison of theoretical and experimental G_{IRs} values

COMPOSITE	THEORETICAL	MEASURED
Unstitched GFRP	-	$0.67 \pm 0.11 \text{ kJ/m}^2$
GFRP stitched to low density in parallel direction	1.55 kJ/m^2	$1.73 \pm 0.20 \text{ kJ/m}^2$
GFRP stitched to low density in normal direction	1.55 kJ/m^2	$1.63 \pm 0.12 \text{ kJ/m}^2$
GFRP stitched to high density in parallel direction	2.45 kJ/m^2	$2.27 \pm 0.21 \text{ kJ/m}^2$
GFRP stitched to high density in normal direction	2.45 kJ/m^2	$1.90 \pm 0.13 \text{ kJ/m}^2$

Fig. 4: SEM micrographs of stitches located (a) 2.5 mm, (b) 10 mm and (c) 25 mm behind the crack front as well as (d) a broken stitch on the fracture surface of a DCB specimen. The direction of crack growth is to the left

The fractured DCB specimens were examined in cross-section using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to observe the delamination crack growth process and the failure mechanisms of the stitches. The delamination grew along the chopped glass mat layer at the mid-plane of the DCB specimen, and this promoted pull-out and bridging of these fibres

behind the crack front. This toughening process is responsible for the relatively high interlaminar fracture toughness of the unstitched GFRP. When the delamination reached a stitch it was deflected along the stitch/GFRP interface for 1-2 mm (Fig. 4a). This appeared to arrest the crack until a higher load caused the delamination to grow around the stitch without causing any damage to the Kevlar[®]. From this observation it appears that the crack tip deflection process contributes to the toughening of the GFRP by stitching. The undamaged stitches formed a crack bridging zone which extended for ~6 mm and 10-15 mm in the composites stitched to the low and high densities, respectively. The length of the bridging zone is the same or slightly longer than that predicted by the model ($\Delta a = 8$ mm). Towards the end of the bridging zone the Kevlar[®] filaments began to fail (Fig. 4b) shortly before complete tensile fracture of the stitch (Fig. 4c). Examination of the fracture surfaces revealed that filaments from the broken threads were pulled-out (Fig. 4d), and this is expected to contribute a small amount to the toughening of the stitched composites.

Mode II Interlaminar Fracture Properties

Fig. 5 compares R-curves for the stitched composites experimentally measured under Mode II loading against the theoretical R-curves calculated using equation 5. It is important to note that R-curves measured for the same composite showed considerable scatter, and this is represented in the figure by error bars. The theoretical R-curves are characterised by a small increase in G_{IIR} within the first 8 mm of crack growth, and then a steady-state crack growth condition exists for longer crack lengths. The measured R-curves also show an initial rise in G_{IIR} , which occurs over the first 15-20 mm. This is mainly from the bridging effect caused by the in-plane glass fibres of the chopped glass mat layer. The experimental curves then show a region where G_{IIR} remains constant or declines gradually with increasing crack length. This region is due to near steady-state crack growth, and the G_{IIRs} values measured from this region are compared with theoretical values in Table 2. This Table and Fig. 5 show that neither the stitch density nor stitch direction influenced the measured Mode II delamination toughness of the GFRP. The model, on the other hand, predicted a small improvement in toughness with increasing stitch density. However, considering the large amount of scatter with the measured G_{IIR} values, the model predicted the Mode II delamination toughness with reasonably good accuracy.

Table 2: Comparison of theoretical and experimental G_{IIRs} values

COMPOSITE	THEORETICAL	MEASURED
Unstitched GFRP	-	6.2 ± 0.4 kJ/m ²
GFRP stitched to low density in parallel direction	6.9 kJ/m ²	5.9 ± 0.4 kJ/m ²
GFRP stitched to low density in normal direction	6.9 kJ/m ²	6.0 ± 0.9 kJ/m ²
GFRP stitched to high density in parallel direction	7.6 kJ/m ²	6.6 ± 0.6 kJ/m ²
GFRP stitched to high density in normal direction	7.6 kJ/m ²	5.9 ± 0.4 kJ/m ²

Fig. 5: Theoretical and measured Mode II R-curves for the GFRP composites stitched to a (a) low and (b) high stitch density. The theoretical R-curves are shown by the solid line

The inability of stitching to improve the Mode II fracture toughness was probably due to the intrinsically high toughness of the unstitched GFRP laminate. SEM examination of this composite after ENC testing showed that delamination crack growth occurred along the chopped glass mat layer located at the mid-plane of the specimen. This promoted extensive bridging of the chopped glass fibres across the opposing fracture surfaces behind the crack front. High shear forces would be needed to pull-out and break these fibres, causing a

substantial improvement in interlaminar toughness. Another feature of the fracture surfaces was their reasonably high roughness caused by the delamination weaving through the chopped glass mat layer. In the ENC tests it was observed that this roughness often caused the opposing fracture surfaces to interlock at high asperities, and increased loading was needed to shear these asperities before crack growth could continue. This toughening caused by surface traction combined with fibre bridging appear to be responsible for the high delamination resistance of the unstitched GFRP. The modelling reveals that the contribution to toughening from stitching was much less, and as a result the delamination resistance of the stitched composites were similar to the unstitched laminate.

Interlaminar fracture studies using the end notched flexure (ENF) test report that the Mode II delamination resistance of unidirectional CFRP composites is improved by stitching [2,7,8]. The G_{IIc} values of unstitched CFRP composites ($\sim 1.5 \text{ kJ/m}^2$) are much lower than the unstitched GFRP (6.2 kJ/m^2). This is because unidirectional laminates do not experience large amounts of fibre bridging and surface traction under shear loading. Stitching is then able to improve the fracture toughness by forming a bridging zone behind the crack front. For example, Jain [2] found that the G_{IIc} value for an unstitched CFRP laminate was 1.3 kJ/m^2 , and this increased to 5.2 kJ/m^2 after stitching with Kevlar[®] yarn to a density of 12 stitches/cm². While this improvement in delamination resistance is considerable, the toughness of the stitched CFRP composite is still lower than the unstitched GFRP. As a result, the ability of stitching to improve the already tough GFRP laminate is lower than for a unidirectional CFRP composite.

After the ENC tests the stitched specimens were examined by SEM to identify the failure mechanism of the Kevlar[®] stitches under shear loading. Fig. 6 shows the stitches at various distances behind the crack front. When the delamination reached a stitch it was deflected along the interface between the thread and surrounding GFRP, and this fracture process was similar in appearance to that observed under Mode I loading (Fig. 4a). The crack then spread around the stitch without causing any damage. At a short distance ($\Delta a = 6 \text{ mm}$) behind the crack front the stitches began to split along their length (Fig. 6b). This splitting spread across the stitch (Fig. 6c) leading to complete failure (Fig. 6d). The length over which the stitches bridged the delamination was observed to be $\sim 20\text{-}25 \text{ mm}$ for the two stitch directions and stitch densities. This stitch bridging zone was longer than that predicted by the model ($\sim 8 \text{ mm}$), but it corresponds to the region on the measured R-curves where the G_{IIIc} increased with crack length for the first $\sim 25 \text{ mm}$. It appears, therefore, that the initial increase in the R-curves is due to the formation of the stitch bridging zone as well as the chopped glass fibre bridging zone. It is worth noting that other Mode II delamination toughness studies [2,7,8] on stitched composites have used the ENF test method rather than the ENC technique. A limitation of the ENF method is that the crack can only be grown for $\sim 25\text{-}30 \text{ mm}$, which is slightly longer than the length of the stitch bridging zone. In comparison, the maximum crack length with the ENC test is about $70\text{-}90 \text{ mm}$, and for this reason the ENC method is a better technique for measuring the steady state fracture toughness of stitched composites.

Fig. 6: Scanning electron micrographs showing increasing amounts of shear-type damage to the Kevlar stitches at distances (Δa) of (a) 3.5 mm, (b) 6 mm, (c) 15 mm and (d) 25 mm. The direction of crack growth is to the left

CONCLUSIONS

Theoretical models developed by Jain and Mai have been shown experimentally to calculate the Mode I and Mode II interlaminar fracture properties of stitched GFRP composites with reasonably good accuracy. The models are capable of predicting various fracture parameters, including the length of the stitch bridging zone, the shape of the R-curve, and the G_{IRs} and G_{IIRs} values. The Mode I fracture toughness of the GFRP composites was improved by stitching because of three toughening mechanisms: stitch bridging zone, crack deflection at the stitches, and pull-out of broken filaments from the stitches. The Mode II delamination was not improved appreciably by stitching because of the intrinsically high toughness of the unstitched GFRP laminate.

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